

The potential of small-scale turbines and microbial fuel cells to support persistent oceanographic sensors

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Abstract—This work explores the potential of ocean renewable energy technologies to support persistent oceanographic sensing. We consider two cases: (1) energy from currents in four straits in the Philippines, extracted by a small-scale turbine, and (2) energy from microbial metabolism in global sediments, extracted by microbial fuel cells. For each energy capture device, we apply performance models based on laboratory experiments to real-world oceanographic data to estimate harvestable power. To illustrate utility for the oceanographic community, we relate the harvestable power to its ability to support generic ocean sensing devices such as an acoustic modem sensor package and unmanned, underwater vehicles.

Keywords—ocean renewable energy; energy capture; small-scale energy capture device, turbine; microbial fuel cell

I. INTRODUCTION

One of the biggest challenges the oceanographic community faces is sparseness of data. As technology has developed through the years, our strategies for oceanographic sensing have evolved. While the community still takes point measurements from ships and moorings, we are beginning to see a shift to datasets with broader spatial coverage. Satellites provide synoptic measurements of large areas of the surface ocean, while wide-spread Argo floats and unmanned underwater vehicles (UUVs) have begun to sample the depths. The future of ocean data collection is showing itself to be distributed sensor packages which persist to sample through time.

The challenge to persistent ocean sensing is the need for power. Battery life currently limits the useful duration of most oceanographic sensing equipment. However, many of these instruments have modest power requirements, making recharging them with locally-extracted, renewable ocean energy a feasible option. Such recharge is now even possible wirelessly [1].

Much research effort is going into developing a wide variety of energy capture devices, with a focus on optimizing harvesting efficiency and durability. The trend has been away from mega-scale devices aiming to supply megawatts of energy, and towards large-scale energy harvesting devices aiming to supply watts to kilowatts. Small-scale devices are

less costly to manufacture, test, and revise, making them an attractive platform for technology development. The oceanographic research community is in an ideal position to be an early adopter of these technologies.

This paper presents a preliminary analysis of the potential of ocean energy capture devices to supply sufficient energy to support persistent oceanographic sensor packages. Specifically, we focus on two classes of energy: energy from currents, extracted by a small-scale turbine in the Philippines (Section II); and energy from bacterial metabolism in sediments, extracted by microbial fuel cells (MFCs) (Section III). For each energy type, we estimate the amount of energy available in the environment, as well as the amount of energy these devices could realistically capture for storage or use. To illustrate utility for the oceanographic community, we present energy captured in terms of ability to support generic ocean sensing devices such as acoustic modem sensor packages and unmanned underwater vehicles (UUVs).

II. ENERGY FROM CURRENTS, EXTRACTED BY A SMALL-SCALE TURBINE

A. Theoretical Energy

The amount of energy theoretically available in the environment, the kinetic energy density, is calculated as:

$$P_{\text{currents}} = [1/2] * \rho * V^3 \quad (1)$$

where ρ is the average density of seawater and V is the magnitude of the water velocity. Velocity data are from the Office of Naval Research “Characterization and Modeling of Archipelago Strait Dynamics” study, also called the Philippine Straits Dynamics Experiment (PhilEx) [2]. PhilEx includes a 15-18 month time series of mooring measurements in Mindoro, Tablas, Dipolog, and Panay straits, which connect the South China Sea to the Sulu Sea. The associated velocity data are described in [3].

The kinetic energy density for the four straits is shown in Figure 1. The depth axis reflects the sill depth of each strait: Mindoro (460m), Tablas (563m), Dipolog (490m), and Panay (578m). Data is missing at the surface due to surface reflection contamination in the ADCP data, and Tablas Strait is missing due to a flooded ADCP. Temporal variability in the straits is

Fig. 1. Theoretical energy (kinetic energy density) available from currents in the four Philippines straits of a) Mindoro, b) Tablas, c) Dipolog, and d) Panay. Note the different X-axes, and the different colorbar on Panay Strait.

Fig. 2. Estimated harvestable energy extractable via a UW field-scale, helical cross-flow microturbine in the four Philippines straits of a) Mindoro, b) Tablas, c) Dipolog, and d) Panay. Note the different X-axes, and the different colorbar on Panay Strait.

dominated by the Northeast (May to September) and Southwest Monsoons (November to March). In Mindoro, the upper waters are monsoon-driven, resulting in fast northward velocities in summer and fast southward velocities in winter [3]. These strong velocities result in greater power availability in during the monsoon seasons. Panay Strait has the greatest velocities, and thus kinetic energy density, seen in the four straits. Here bottom velocities are strong, greater than 1 m s^{-1} , and below 490m the flow is always uni-directional southward towards the Sulu Sea [3]. This makes Panay Strait an attractive source for ocean renewable energy; the average power density below 490m is $235 \pm 18 \text{ W m}^{-2}$.

Note that the mooring deployment was in calendar year 2008, a strong La Niña year. During La Niña conditions, water velocities and associated estimates of kinetic energy density are lower than usual. Thus, energy density is expected to be higher in normal conditions.

B. Harvestable Energy

While estimates of kinetic energy density are useful for understanding how much energy exists in the environment in a given a location, it doesn't reflect how much energy we could realistically capture for use. The amount of energy able to be captured from ocean currents using a turbine can be expressed as:

$$P_{\text{harvestable}} = [1/2] * \rho * V^3 * C_p * D * H \quad (2)$$

where ρ is the density of the seawater, V is the magnitude of the water velocity, C_p is a measure of the total efficiency of the turbine, D is the diameter of the turbine, and H is the height of the turbine.

The total efficiency, C_p , varies from device to device. Here we consider a four-bladed helical cross-flow "microturbine" developed by the University of Washington (UW) [4,5]. The full-sized field scale device is 1.013 m tall and 0.724 m in diameter with a cross-sectional area of 0.733 m^2 ; the laboratory scale device is 1/17th size, at 0.234 m tall and 0.172 m in diameter with a cross-sectional area of 0.040 m^2 . We developed a performance model based on UW's laboratory flume tests with the laboratory scale device. At tilt angles less than or equal to 30 degrees such as would be experienced by a bottom-mounted turbine, the cut-in speed is 0.47 m s^{-1} and the cut-out speed is 0.21 m s^{-1} . Total efficiency varied from 6.7% at 0.4 m s^{-1} up to 24% at 0.8 m s^{-1} [4,5]. Velocities greater than 0.8 m s^{-1} were unable to be tested in the lab, so for this study device efficiency at greater velocities was held at 24%, despite the general relationship that device efficiency increases with current velocity.

The estimated harvestable power in watts from placing one field-sized UW microturbine in each of the four straits is shown in Figure 2. For these calculations field-scale device efficiencies are assumed to equal to laboratory-scale device efficiencies, though this may not be the case [4,5].

C. Support for Ocean Sensors

1) Acoustic Modem Transmissions

To give context to the harvestable energy estimates (Fig. 2),

Fig. 3. Charge time in days with depth for a 200 mW-hr acoustic modem transition in a) Mindoro, b) Tablas, c) Dipolog, and d) Panay straits.

we relate this energy to generic ocean sensing equipment that it could support. Fig. 3 shows the time in days necessary to build up enough battery charge for a generic 200 mW acoustic modem transmission, using one UW microturbine for energy capture. In general, deep waters just above the sill support regular transmissions. In Mindoro Strait, the average charge

Fig. 4. Days to accumulate enough energy to recharge a 5 kW-hr mid-size UUV battery in Panay Strait, using one microturbine. Mean (solid black), standard deviation (dotted black), and maximum (red) is calculated over calendar year 2008.

time below 400 m is 1.8 ± 3.3 days, while at the deepest measurement (440 m), the average charge time is only 0.15 ± 0.11 days, and the maximum time is 0.47 days for calendar year 2008. In Dipolog Strait, the average charge time below 400m is 2.2 ± 3.2 days, while at the deepest measurement (450m), the average charge time is 0.46 ± 0.71 days, with a maximum charge time of 6.5 days in calendar year 2008. Finally, for Panay Strait, the average charge time below 490 m is 1.7 ± 1.2 days, while at the deepest measurement (550 m), the average charge time is 1.5 ± 1.1 days, with a maximum charge time of 6.7 days. Similar calculations for Tablas strait are not given as deep data were lost due to the flooded ADCP.

2) UUV Battery Recharges

Because the currents at depth in Panay Strait are relatively swift and consistent, this location can support more energy-intensive oceanographic sensing equipment. Fig. 4 shows the time in days necessary to build up enough energy to recharge a mid-sized unmanned, underwater vehicle (UUV) with a 5 kW-hr battery, using one UW microturbine. For comparison, the Bluefin-12S uses a 4.5 kWh battery pack, while the Remus 600 uses a 5.4 kW-hr battery pack. Between 500 and 550 m, the average time to recharge a 5 kW-hr battery is 7.6 ± 4.7 days; the maximum time ever required in that depth range in calendar year 2008 is 37.6 days.

III. ENERGY FROM MICROBIAL METABOLISM, EXTRACTED BY MICROBIAL FUEL CELLS

We also evaluated the potential for microbial fuel cells (MFCs) to support ongoing oceanographic measurements, based on laboratory tests of fuel cells in development at SPAWAR. Microbial fuel cell technology isn't advanced enough to be able to calculate the amount of energy theoretically available in the environment as distinct from the amount of energy attainable from specific fuel cell prototype. Instead, we first discuss the relationship between power output and environmental conditions in the laboratory setting, and then extrapolate the results to predictions of power output on a global scale. Finally, we place the results in the context of their ability to support oceanographic sensing equipment.

A. Power Output results from the Lab

Microbial fuel cell power density is known to depend on a number of environmental factors including: the concentration and quality (lability) of the total organic carbon (TOC) in the sediment, the bacterial community in the sediment, the permeability of the sediment, the temperature, and the oxygen concentration in the overlying water. TOC is important to fuel cell performance as it is the nominative electron supplier to the anaerobic bacteria living in the sediments. MFC power output also depends on the composition of the anode and cathode, the geometry and size of the anode and cathode, and the efficiency of the energy-harvesting electronics [6].

We placed fuel cells in sediments in a laboratory water bath [7], and measured the power output in relationship to varying temperature and total organic carbon (TOC) conditions. Specifically, sediment samples were collected in the Southern California Bight between San Diego and Santa Barbara, CA, at depths of 1188 m, 1228 m and 2002 m in 2014. The TOC in the sediments was 3.6% by weight in the 1188 m sample, 1% in the 1228m sample, and 2.1% in the 2002 sample. Triplicate fuel cells, composed of small carbon cloth anodes and a common large carbon cloth cathode, were implanted into the sediments. The sediments with the fuel cells were then immersed in bubbled seawater at temperatures ranging from -1°C to 12°C for a period of 18 months.

The results are shown in Fig. 5 below. Power density (power output per anode area) increases with increasing temperature and TOC. Power output is continuous from a microbial fuel cell. Power density [$\mu\text{W m}^{-2}$] was fit with a simple linear model against TOC at 2°C and 4°C , yielding the following equations:

$$\text{Power Density}_{(2^{\circ}\text{C})} = (143.49 \times \text{TOC}) + 168.11 \quad (3)$$

$$\text{Power Density}_{(4^{\circ}\text{C})} = (186.96 \times \text{TOC}) + 144.26 \quad (4)$$

Fig. 5 Laboratory microbial fuel cell output as a function of TOC and temperature from three deep sea sediment samples at temperatures ranging from 2 to 10.5°C . Error bars indicate one standard deviation.

These equations describing the relationship between power output and the environment can be used to estimate performance in other conditions.

Overall, the laboratory work provides a reasonable estimate of power output from deep sea sediments, which we have seen mimics output from in-situ studies [9]. We have not found pressures up to 500 atmospheres to be important in laboratory measurements, though tested sediments collected from depth were de-pressurized and warmed during recovery [Richter, unpublished].

Fig. 6. Global predictions of power from microbial fuel cells (MFCs). a) Global total organic carbon (TOC) by % weight in ocean sediments, used to predict MFC performance. b) MFC power output [$\mu\text{W m}^{-2}$] at 2°C. c) Calculated MFC power output difference [$\mu\text{W m}^{-2}$] between 2°C and 4°C. d) MFC charge time in days for an acoustic modem transmission requiring 200 mW.

B. Global Power Predictions

Using the relationship between power density, TOC, and temperature (eq. 3 and 4), we extrapolated our laboratory results to predict power output globally. The global TOC data used are shown in Fig. 6a. The data were interpolated from over 5,500 data points [9]. TOC concentrations are by percent weight, and based on primary production, bathymetry, river inputs, and in-situ TOC measurements. Fig. 6b shows projected power output from a microbial fuel cell employing a 1 m² carbon cloth anode, operating at 2°C. While actual sea surface sediment temperatures will vary, particularly in shallower regions where temperatures may be expected to be warmer, Fig. 6c shows that the difference in power derived at 2°C vs 4°C is typically less than 100 $\mu\text{W m}^{-2}$.

C. Support for Ocean Sensors

In order to place the global power predictions from microbial fuel cells in a more useful context, Fig. 6d shows the time in days necessary for a 1 m² microbial fuel cell anode to build up enough battery charge for a generic 200 mW acoustic modem transmission. This is days per 1 m² microbial fuel cell anode. The majority of deep ocean basins are estimated to require from one to two months, while coastal areas may take as little as ten days.

IV. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

This work looked at the potential of two different types of ocean energy capture devices to support persistent oceanographic sensing equipment. Estimates of energy capture by a single small-scale turbine (1 m tall by 0.7 m diameter) suggest that the energy supply in the four Philippine straits of Mindoro, Dipolog, Panay, and Tablas is sufficient for sub-daily to multi-daily acoustic modem transmissions. At depth in Panay Strait, where tidal currents are consistently strong, energy obtained by a single turbine is estimated sufficient to recharge a mid-sized UUV battery roughly weekly. Energy generated from microbial fuel cells in ocean sediments also shows potential to support oceanographic sensing equipment, although minimally. In near shore areas we estimate that a 1 m² microbial fuel cell has a charge time of several weeks in order to accumulate enough energy for a typical acoustic modem transmission; in the pelagic oceans the time required is estimated to be a few months. Though the scope of this study is currently limited, preliminary results suggest that small-scale ocean renewable energy technologies have the potential to change the way oceanographic measurements are taken, by supporting more persistent oceanographic sensing equipment.

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